

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PRODUCTION AND MANAGEMENT METHODS OF DOMESTIC WASTEWATER IN THE DEPARTMENT OF NIORO DU RIP

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Abstract

Wastewater management and sanitation in general are essential drivers of economic development and the well-being of urban populations in Senegal. Despite considerable efforts in this sector, the coverage rate of essential wastewater collection and management services (sewer systems, modern latrines, soakaways, etc.) remains low in both urban and rural areas. This study contributes to the analysis of the domestic wastewater sanitation system in the Nioro department. To conduct this study, we used a mixed-methods data collection approach, combining quantitative and qualitative surveys with 664 residents of the Nioro department within the RIP (Regional Information Platform). Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the head of the Nioro hygiene brigade (1), the regional sanitation service (1), and the private contractors (5) responsible for wastewater collection and disposal. To assess the average volume of wastewater produced by households, the volume of containers in latrines was considered in this study. The results reveal autonomous or individual methods of managing domestic and rainwater wastewater in the Nioro department of the RIP. 82.8% dispose of domestic wastewater in the streets, 12.4% in uninhabited areas or abandoned houses, and 3.9% in septic tanks. Also, due to the lack of a collective wastewater treatment system, sewage disposal is ensured by vacuum trucks and... *Baye-Pèle* These different methods of wastewater management reveal unsustainable practices and environmental and health issues.

Keywords: Management, Domestic wastewater, Sanitation, Water production, Nioro du RIP.

Introduction:

Urban agglomerations in sub-Saharan Africa, and in the Sahel in particular, are grappling with stormwater management problems due to topographical limitations and the effects of rapid urbanization. In these cities, sustainable stormwater management remains a significant challenge for local elected officials responsible for urban planning and concerned with ensuring the safety and comfort of city residents (Ndongo, 2015). Pollution, climate change, conflicts, water-related disasters, and demographic shifts are creating unprecedented pressure on water resources in many regions of the world (Hounguè, 2020). Wastewater treatment is a current concern in developing countries. The impact of rainwater has increased with the emergence of peripheral neighborhoods (resulting from urban sprawl in sub-Saharan Africa) born from demographic pressure (Malouono and Berton, 2018). In subtropical Africa, the inability of public institutions to react quickly and effectively to unprecedented population growth and massive rural exodus has had adverse effects, including oversaturation of already inadequate sanitation infrastructure (Ngahane, 2015). The exorbitant costs of building public sanitation infrastructure mean that many African cities today lack modern sanitation systems and/or have latrines that do not meet WHO standards. Urban drainage is a common problem in Sahelian cities; the heavy investment required to address it leads to the development of poor practices whose impacts are often poorly understood (Ndongo *et al.*, 2015). Remediation is the process of removing, reducing, or neutralizing contaminants from a site in order to prevent or

minimize adverse effects on the current or future environment. It also encompasses all the techniques for collecting wastewater and treating it before discharge into the natural environment (Triplet, 2017). Wastewater in African cities poses a significant threat to the quality of surface and groundwater resources and to biodiversity, due to the limited availability of adequate treatment systems and low investment in this sector. Managing wastewater, by intensifying wastewater collection and treatment (on-site and off-site), can contribute to achieving the goals set by the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (Hounguè, 2020). It is, in fact, the only water resource that will grow in the future. Its consideration is therefore essential, and its development must consequently be integrated into sustainable development goals, if it is treated (Leila, 2014).

Like other Senegalese cities, the challenges related to the collection, management, and disposal of domestic wastewater are also a concern in the Kaolack region, and particularly in the Nioro du Rip department. This department, like other Senegalese cities, lacks a collective wastewater treatment infrastructure. This study analyzes the methods of domestic wastewater production and management through an analytical approach based on household perception surveys in the Nioro du Rip department. This work is doubly relevant due to the limited coverage of sewage systems in two-thirds of Senegalese cities and the urgent need to achieve SDG 6.1 by 2030.

Study framework:

The Nioro department lacks centralized sewage systems and rainwater drainage networks in all its mu-

municipalities. Consequently, households rely on individual wastewater management systems and septic tanks, depending on available resources, according to the household heads interviewed.

Like other departments, Nioro struggles to address sanitation issues, particularly wastewater management. The sanitation problem in Senegal is primarily technical and financial. Currently, local authorities lack sufficient financial and technical resources to construct

public wastewater and solid waste collection points. Installing a collective sanitation system is expensive, as is maintaining the network. This is one of the reasons why the Nioro Department does not have a domestic and stormwater wastewater treatment system. While the construction of public wastewater treatment facilities is indeed the responsibility of the State, some local authorities could fully manage this if they had substantial financial resources.

Figure 1: Location of the communes of the Nioro Department of the RIP.

I. Methodology

The methodological approach adopted is based on the collection of socioeconomic data (interviews and household surveys) and in situ analyses of the waters of the hydraulic infrastructures of the eight (8) municipalities of study.

1.1. Collection and processing of institutional data

Demographic data and data from water management structures were used in this study. This data was processed using Excel spreadsheets and ArcGIS software for cartographic representation.

Hydrological data These are the Directorate of Water Resources Management and Planning (DGPRES), the National Water Company of Senegal (SONES), the Senegalese Water Company (SDE) and the Rural Drilling Office (OFOR). Detailed hydrological maps were also consulted at the DGPRES.

Demographic data The data were collected at the National Agency for Statistics and Demography (ANSD). Most of it comes from studies and the fourth general census of population, housing, agriculture, and livestock (RGPHAE) in 2013. Other specific works by various authors also contributed to providing reliable statistical data. This data quantitatively represents the population trends in the Nioro department. It was supplemented by cartographic data obtained from the National Agency for Territorial Development (ANAT) and the Ecological Monitoring Center (CSE) in 2016.

1.2. Fieldwork and investigations

1.2.1. Exploratory or pre-investigation visits

Direct observations were carried out in the field to observe water supply infrastructure, to assess the difficulties of access to drinking water for households, the level of service in drinking water distribution networks in municipalities, the quality of water distributed by actors in the sector, the sanitation system and the living environment.

The preliminary investigation is The field test phase involved eighty (80) questionnaires submitted to heads of households in the communes of Gainte Kaye, Nioro, Porokhane, Taïba Niassène, Paoskoto, Keur Maba, Médina Sabakh, and Darou Salam. The aim was to verify the relevance of the proposed questions and to identify potential biases and inconsistencies.

1.2.2. Criteria for selecting survey sites, sampling techniques and the conduct of socio-economic surveys

Working at the departmental level led us to choose the purposive sampling technique. Thus, we selected 8 out of 15 municipalities based on a defined criterion in order to align with the established research hypotheses (Table 1).

The choice of the 8 municipalities is made according to three (3) criteria:

The presence of a water supply network: this criterion allows us to determine the number of localities with access to a water supply network (WSN) and the management problems they may face.

The absence of a water supply network: it allows us to identify the localities that have the most problems in terms of access to water, both in terms of quantity and quality.

Supply from a locality with a supply network: this allows us to understand the dependence of certain localities on their neighbors with a supply network. Based on these criteria, our study focuses on 8 municipalities (Table 1). These are listed in the following table:

Table 1

Municipalities of the Nioro department and their characteristics

Municipalities	Populations	Number of households
Nioro du Rip	20784	2363
Paoskoto	2658	238
Porokhane	5694	532
Dabaly	1228	154
Taïba Niasséne	7174	568
Keur Madiabel	10542	1050
Keur Maba	1126	93
Medina Sabakh	5381	613
Keur Mandongo	1303	98
Ndramé Stopover	2241	252
Wack Ngouna	3825	358
Gainte Kaye	1311	149
Darou Salam	1898	166
Ngayéne	180	2427
Kayemor	158	2259

1.2.3. Sampling techniques

Sampling is based on household size in eight (8) targeted communes in the Nioro du Rip department (4722 households). To determine the sample size, Bernoulli's sampling formula was used, according to the following equation:

$$n = \frac{(Z)^2 \times N}{(Z)^2 + \alpha^2 \times (N - 1)}$$

With n being the sample size; N being the size of the universe investigated (or parent population); α being the width of the range expressing the margin of error; Z being the standard value corresponding to the chosen confidence level.

$$n = \frac{2,576^2 \times 4722}{2,576^2 + 0,1^2 \times (4722 - 1)}$$

For this study, the parent population (N) is 4722 households for the 8 selected municipalities. The Z-value, corresponding to the chosen 90% confidence

level, is 2.576, with α representing the width of the 5% margin of error range (0.05), which gives (2*5%) 10% (0.1). Therefore, the study is based on a sample of 664 households, representing 14% of the parent population, with a confidence or uncertainty interval of approximately 5%.

To distribute the 664 households to be interviewed (which constitute the sample size) according to the 8 selected villages, a quota sample was chosen and the number of households to be interviewed per village is calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Nombre de ménages de la commune} \times 664}{\text{Nombre total de ménages des 8 communes}}$$

Table 1 below shows the distribution of the sample according to the four districts.

Table 2

Sampling distribution

Villages	Number of Households	Uncertainty interval	Sampling	Percentage
Darou Salam	166	5%	23	3.5
Nioro du Rip	2363	5%	332	50.0
Medina Sabakh	613	5%	86	13.0
Paoskoto	238	5%	33	5.0
Gainte Kaye	149	5%	21	3.2
Porokhane	532	5%	75	11.3
Taiba Niassene	568	5%	80	12.0
Keur Maba Diakhou	93	5%	13	2.0
Total	4722	5%	664	100

1.2.4. Interview Procedure

Interviews conducted with NGOs, municipalities, technical services (SDE, SONES), ASUFOR, ADC, ASC, and CDQ highlighted the diversity of actors involved in water management in Nioro. They also revealed the sources of supply, the condition of boreholes, governance structures, and socio-economic constraints that encourage the use of wells of dubious quality. Through this diverse range of actors, the interviews underscored the difficulties encountered in local management and the social tensions generated by the commercialization of drinking water, reflecting the technical, institutional, and social challenges related to equitable access to this resource.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Typology and composition of domestic wastewater

Domestic wastewater results from daily water use within households. It is subdivided into greywater and blackwater, which generally carries organic pollution. Its composition varies according to household practices, the volume of water consumed, and the socio-economic profile of the inhabitants. The daily pollutant load per individual, estimated based on consumption between 15 and 110 liters, illustrates the strong dependence of the quality and quantity of wastewater on the characteristics of the dwelling (Hamon, 1983).

Table 3

Average quantitative and qualitative characteristics of domestic wastewater according to (Hamon, 1983).

	Volume (l/inhabitant/day)	BOD5 mg/l/inhabitant/day	MY (mg/l/inhabitant/day)
Wastewater	15 to 25	15 to approximately 600	10 to approximately 400
Household wastewater	50 to 110	40 to approximately 500	30 to approximately 350

Suspended solids (SS) in domestic wastewater are generally expressed in milligrams per liter (mg/L). They consist of undissolved particles larger than 1 μm in diameter, comprising both mineral and organic elements. These particles have the characteristic of settling spontaneously through sedimentation. Household wastewater is characterized by a diversity of components, including dissolved solids, the majority of which are in diluted form.

2.1.1. Knowledge of the nature of household wastewater.

Greywater constitutes a specific category of domestic wastewater, produced by daily activities such as meal preparation, personal washing, and toilet use. Its composition is characterized by significant heterogeneity, incorporating organic matter (fats, proteins, food scraps), chemical substances from cleaning products and detergents, as well as suspended solids including mineral particles (soil, sand) and waste of animal or plant origin. Emulsified fats and dissolved compounds such as mineral salts and soluble organic matter are also present. The definition proposed by Vaillant (1973), adopted by Ndiaye (2013), highlights the diversity of pollutants present in greywater and underscores the environmental and health challenges associated with its management, particularly in terms of aquatic contamination, microbiological risks, and eutrophication.

2.1.2. Knowledge of the nature of wastewater

Wastewater refers to domestic effluents from toilets, containing feces and urine. It has a complex composition of biodegradable organic matter (cellulose, lipids, proteins, carbohydrates, fatty acids, uric acid, amino acids, alcohols) and minerals (Vaillant, 1973). It is characterized by a high microbiological load, including pathogenic intestinal flora, notably coliforms and fecal streptococci used as contamination indicators (SPGE, 2010). This wastewater poses a major health risk due to the presence of viruses (diarrhea, gastroen-

teritis), bacteria (cholera, dysentery, typhoid), and parasites (worm eggs), which explains why individual sanitation systems have long focused primarily on its treatment (Sall, 1998). Chemically, they are also heavily loaded with nitrogenous pollutants, particularly organic and ammoniacal nitrogen from urine, estimated at approximately 4 g per user per day (Hamon, 1983). Considered the most polluted and dangerous domestic wastewater, sewage requires rigorous management to limit health and environmental risks.

2.2. Production and volumes of water discharged

In analyzing water supply and consumption parameters, estimating the volume of wastewater discharged relies on identifying and quantifying household practices. Key factors include laundry frequency, the number of basins used for each load and for washing dishes, and the toilet flushing method. These parameters allow for a direct link between daily water use and the volume of wastewater produced, thus providing a methodological basis for assessing domestic discharges and planning sanitation systems.

2.2.1. Disposal of household wastewater

In the Nioro du Rip department, the lack of institutional systems for collecting and disposing of domestic wastewater leads households to adopt independent management practices. Household wastewater (from washing, bathing, dishwashing, and cooking) is predominantly discharged into the streets by 82.8% of households, creating health risks related to stagnation and the proliferation of waterborne diseases. A minority of households resort to other solutions: 12.4% discharge it into uninhabited areas, 3.9% into septic tanks, and only 0.9% into soakaways—marginal practices within the sample studied (Fig. 2). These results highlight the predominance of uncontrolled discharges and the inadequacy of sanitation infrastructure, exacerbating the challenges to public health and environmental sustainability.

Figure 2: Methods of domestic wastewater disposal, author surveys, 2021.

2.2.2. Production of washing water

In the Nioro du Rip department, laundry is a particularly water-intensive domestic activity. The survey reveals that 44.4% (Fig. 3) of households report doing laundry more than three times a month, 37.4% three times a month, and 17.5% twice a month. Marginal

practices involve 0.5% of households doing laundry once a month and 0.2% (Fig. 3) outsourcing this task to washerwomen. This high frequency reflects significant water consumption, which, once discharged, is mostly dumped into the streets, fields, or other undeveloped areas.

Figure 3: Number of washes per month, surveys authors, 2021.

2.2.3. Number of basins of water per load of laundry

Domestic water consumption related to laundry varies significantly between households, depending on the level of soiling of the clothes and the nature of the users' professional activities. Surveys conducted in the Nioro du Rip department reveal that 42.7% of households use an average of four basins of water per load, while a significant proportion use three basins, followed by those using two. Furthermore, 27.9% (Fig. 4)

of households report using more than four basins, indicating particularly high consumption. Conversely, a small segment of the population (0.6%) outsources this task by hiring housekeepers to wash clothes. This distribution highlights the heterogeneity of water consumption practices, directly correlated with socio-professional conditions and household habits.

Figure 4: Number of basins of water per load of laundry, surveys authors, 2021.

The greater the number of basins used, the more significant its contribution to the wastewater treatment problem. In other words, the contribution of laundry water to the problem of domestic wastewater treatment depends on the number of washes done and the number of basins of water used. Consequently, this quantity of water, discharged haphazardly into the environment, poses real health and environmental risks in the department. Our survey results show that 57.5% of households dispose of their laundry wastewater in the street, 3.9% (Fig. 5) in their yards, and 37.4% in uninhabited

or undeveloped areas. The "non-response" category includes households that do not do their own laundry and send their clothes to women who specifically take care of their laundry. This category represents 1.2% of the results obtained (Fig. 5).

Indeed, all these waste disposal methods adopted by households stem from the lack of collective sanitation infrastructure, namely a sewer system. The ONAS (National Sanitation Office) collective network has not yet reached most of the country's secondary cities. This slow pace of infrastructure development represents a loss in water resource management.

Figure 5: Laundry water disposal site, surveys authors, 2021.

Domestic wastewater from washing dishes or cooking is disposed of in similar ways, reflecting a largely informal and unregulated system. The survey reveals that 62.5% (Fig. 6) of households discharge this wastewater directly into the street, thus exposing public spaces to risks of stagnation and contamination. Furthermore, 34.5% (Fig. 6) of households dispose of it in

uninhabited areas or vacant lots, contributing to diffuse soil pollution and environmental degradation. Less common practices include discharge into property courtyards (2.4%) and the use of soakaways (0.6%), solutions that remain insufficient for ensuring sustainable wastewater management.

Figure 6: Dishwashing and cooking water drainage mode, surveys authors, 2021.

2.2.4. Method of managing pits

The method of supplying water to the toilet affects the process or the time it takes for the septic tank to fill. Indeed, the amount of water used after defecation by households provides additional water for the sanitation system. Analysis of Figure 7 shows that the majority of households surveyed bring water (such as a bucket) to the toilet because they are not equipped with a toilet. This group represents 52.1% of our sample. Next, toilets supplied with water from jerrycans and pots holding approximately 2 to 5 liters of water come in second, representing 37.6% (Fig. 7) of the households surveyed. Toilets with taps represent 2.9%. Those

equipped with a flush system are less common, at 2.1%. Overall, these quantities of water can be considered relatively small in areas where a sewer system exists.

However, when analyzed within the context of our selected or targeted municipalities, characterized by the absence of sanitation and wastewater networks, this can become a real health problem. Therefore, the populations must implement a collective system for the collection, treatment, and disposal of all wastewater produced, which guarantees a healthy living environment and protects their health.

Figure 7: Toilet water supply method, surveys authors, 2021.

2.2.4.1. Nature and management of wastewater collection pits

In the Nioro department, various types of pits have been identified, reflecting a diversity of domestic sanitation practices. The majority of households use septic tanks (82.6%), generally constructed by masons or unskilled tradespeople, raising questions about the technical quality and durability of these structures. Alongside these systems, soakaways (9.5%) and latrines

(7.9%) are also found, though these remain in the minority but demonstrate alternative solutions implemented by the population. However, the lack of fixed overflows and structured drainage systems poses a major environmental risk, promoting soil and groundwater contamination, as well as the proliferation of health hazards.

Figure 8: Category of wastewater collection pits, surveys authors, 2021.

The management of septic tanks constitutes a real sanitation problem in Nioro because the average time for filling septic tanks is not the same for different households.

Thus, after the filling of the septic tanks, emptying is done mainly by truck (76.3%), by manual system (19.4%), 4.3% by motor pump and others (fig. 9).

Figure 9: Types of septic tank emptying, surveys authors, 2021.

2.2.4.2. Emptying of septic tanks by truck

The emptying of domestic septic tanks is carried out using tanker trucks (76.3%) belonging to a private company based in Kaolack. Households pay between 25,000 and 30,000 CFA francs per emptying to obtain their services. However, 30.2% of households encounter difficulties in having their tanks emptied. These difficulties sometimes stem from the fact that this private company only comes after receiving a sufficient number of requests. This slowness on their part is a source of disease and air pollution from these tanks. In contrast, in the municipality of Nioro, the local government also helps households empty their tanks by providing a tanker truck for a fee of 10,000 CFA francs per emptying. However, this is not the case in other municipalities; their municipal authorities informed us that they do not have a sufficient budget to subsidize household septic tank emptying. Furthermore, it is important to note that after emptying, this wastewater is dumped haphazardly in fields on the outskirts of the towns. Similarly, some households, lacking the resources to hire a septic tank emptying truck, resort to other methods such as manual emptying (see Figure 9).

In the municipalities visited, manual emptying of septic tanks is carried out both by household members and by specialists, such as septic tank cleaners. These professionals are paid between 6,000 and 10,000 CFA

francs. To perform this task correctly, it is essential to dig a hole inside or outside the house to collect the sludge from the tank. This practice is considered unacceptable as it fails to meet proper hygiene standards. However, it continues despite municipal bans, leaving the situation critical. To avoid municipal oversight, it is often done at night or discreetly. Similarly, emptying with a motorized pump is not widely used by households, representing only 4.3% of cases. They prefer truck-based emptying, despite the higher cost, and to preserve their living environment.

2.2.4.3. Management of cesspools and latrines

Lost pits represent only 9.5%, they do not have a significant impact in our chosen municipalities. These pits are used to receive wastewater from households and toilets, including fecal matter. They are not emptied; to be more precise, they are not drained, as their name suggests (cesspool). They are mainly located in the streets, sometimes even inside houses. Their proliferation will certainly contribute to groundwater pollution and the destruction of the living environment. Moreover, they are strictly prohibited by municipal authorities, and orders have been issued to their owners to remove them from the streets to protect public health, according to city officials we interviewed.

Latrines (7.9%) are found in all the municipalities in our sample. They are built by the poorest populations, who live in extremely precarious conditions. Furthermore, due to a lack of resources, they cannot afford toilets and cesspools. As a result, these communities are left with only latrines. They report having received no assistance from the municipalities to improve their situation.

2.2.4.4. Filling time of identified pits

In the commune of Nioro, septic tanks do not fill up too quickly. Generally, 79.5% of households have

tanks that fill up once a year. 13.4% (Fig. 10) of households have their tanks filled every six (6) months. Only 7.1% of households have their tanks filled every three (3) months. Finally, the "other" category concerns households whose tanks fill up everyone (1) or two (2) months. Indeed, this slow filling of the tanks considerably reduces the frequency of emptying them. This situation may be linked to the soil structure, which prevents the water table from rising and thus avoids refilling (Fig. 10).

Figure 10: Pit filling time, surveys authors, 2021.

2.2.5. Stormwater wastewater management

One of the key issues for which governments should find a sustainable solution is stormwater management in urban areas (Sané et al., 2019). Indeed, almost all cities in Senegal suffer from problems related to the efficient drainage of rainwater. Linked to climate variability, stormwater management is a challenge for city managers and residents alike. The Nioro du Rip Department is also affected by sanitation problems, including the poor management of stormwater runoff.

This runoff creates significant sanitation problems and alters the morphology of natural channels through gully erosion in some municipalities. As a result, most of the municipalities in the department are disfigured by these gullies caused by poor wastewater and stormwater management and by problems with natural drainage systems. Consequently, homes and infrastructure located near these gullies are subsiding or collapsing.

Photo 1: (A) Undeveloped ravine, exit from the commune of Nioro; (B) Ravine crossing the commune of Nioro already built, authors, August 2021.

2.2.6. Resilience techniques in case of excess rainwater.

Households use traditional methods for rainwater drainage. Survey results indicate that 11.2% of households affected by excess water collect it using buckets or basins. Next, 5.6% of households backfill when there

is excess water in their homes. Thus, their techniques- These methods consist of building embankments to prevent flooding into their properties. Finally, the use of sandbags accounts for 2.6% (Fig. 11), which is the last method used by households in our sample. In short,

the evacuation techniques employed by households affected by the flooding are temporary. Consequently, these methods are considered unconventional and do

not completely resolve the flooding problems. They only provide temporary relief to the population.

Figure 11: Methods adopted in case of flooding, Surveys authors, 2021.

Photo 2: Flooded houses in Taïba Niassene, photo authors, 2021.

Conclusion:

This study on wastewater production and management in the Nioro department reveals significant water usage by the households surveyed, characterized by production methods such as household uses (cooking, washing dishes, laundry, and bathing) and sewage (septic tank waste). Indeed, this increasing water production is practically impossible to quantify at the household level in the Nioro department due to the multitude of collection containers and the diversity of uses. Household wastewater is generally discharged into the streets, according to 82.8% of the households interviewed. A small number of households (12.4%) discharge their wastewater into uninhabited areas. The

volume of wastewater discharged is strongly linked to the volume of water consumed daily by each inhabitant. This volume represents approximately 80% of daily consumption per inhabitant (M. Radoux, 1983). Also, wastewater is collected in septic tanks, soakaways, and latrines, the filling times of which vary depending on the available water supply system and household size. This indicates the complexity of the on-site sanitation practices observed among households in the department. It is further defined by the methods of evacuating wastewater from the tanks, some of which are handled by private contractors (septic tank emptying companies, etc.). *Baye-Pèle''Or* (motor pump operators). Domestic septic tank emptying is carried out using tanker

trucks (76.3%) belonging to a private company based in Kaolack at a cost between 25,000 and 30,000 FCFA. While the ‘‘Baye-Pèle’’ OrFor septic tank emptying using a motor pump, the price is not fixed as it depends on the capacity of the pit and the accessibility of the site.

Overall, the diverse domestic wastewater management practices observed in the Niore department highlight the critical issue of sanitation in Senegalese cities. The lack of public infrastructure can further increase the vulnerability of communities to hygiene-related and waterborne diseases.

References

1. Abeje W. (2000). Sustainable stormwater management through spatial management and subdivision: the case of ADDIS ABABA (ETHIOPIA): Doctoral thesis-URGC-HU, National Institute of Applied Sciences of LYON, 391p.
2. Abulude FO, Fagbayide SD (2018). Water, Sanitation and Poverty in the Changing World. Case of Nigeria. Anabelle Uniiversiitääiidiin Oradea, Seria Geografie, Vol. XXVIII, n°1, pp. 91-96.
3. Dasylyva S., Cosandey C., Sambou. S. (2003). Acuteness of water-related problems and need for "integrated" stormwater management in the area of the dune sands of Dakar, pp.57-75.
4. Dasylyva S., Cosandey C., Orange D. (2002). Proposal for "integrated" stormwater management to combat water-related problems in the suburbs of Dakar, Ouagadougou, Proceedings of the Envirowater Colloquia, pp.207-218.
5. Dione Yangane. (2014). Public participation and policies for access to drinking water in rural Senegal, associations of drinking water network users in the Saint-Louis region, doctoral thesis, University of Toulouse 3 Paul Sabatier (UT3 Paul Sabatier), Doctoral School and specialty Information and Communication Sciences, 316 p.
6. GOMIS O., SOW D., SALL O. (2019). Urban environment and health in the municipality of Ziguinchor (Senegal): the example of the neighborhoods of Néma 2 and Coboda. Revue de géographie du laboratoire Leidi ISSN 0851-2515_N°22_December 2019, pp 280-295.Revuevu.
7. Houngouè, J. (2020). Sustainable management strategies for domestic wastewater in the Commune of Porto-Novo and preservation of its lagoon from urban source pollution [Doctoral thesis, University of Abomey-Calavi]. HAL Open Science. <https://theses.hal.science/tel-05128372>.
8. Leila Mimeche. (2014). Feasibility study of the installation of an urban wastewater treatment plant using planted filters in an arid environment - Application to the Biskra region -, doctoral thesis, Mohamed Khider University – Biskra, Faculty of Science and Technology, 164 p.
9. Malouono Livangou, ML, & Berton Ofoueme, Y. (2018). Stormwater management issues in the peripheral districts of sub-Saharan African cities (Literature review, 2014). Environmental and Water Sciences, Public Health & Territorial Intelligence Journal (EWASH & TI Journal), 2(1), 77-85. <http://revues.imist.ma/?journal=ewash-ti/>.
10. Ndongo, B., Lako Mbouendeu, S., & Hiregued, JP (2015). Socio-health and environmental impacts of stormwater management in a Sahelian urban environment: the case of Maroua, Cameroon. Afriq SCIENCE, 11(1), 237-251. <http://www.afriqscience.info>.
11. Ngahane Emilienne Laure. (2015). Technical management of the environment of a city (Bembèrèkè in Benin), characterization and quantification of solid waste emitted, knowledge of water resources and technical approach, doctoral thesis, University of Liège, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Environmental Sciences and Management, 254 p.
12. RADOUX M. (1983). Emergency technology for urban wastewater treatment. Round Table of the Scientific Research and Policy Committee, November 22-24, Dakar.